

Appendix C: Complete Search strategy

a) First Method

Source	Boolean Search	Search Result	Screening protocol
Scopus	TITLE-ABS-KEY (("healthcare" OR "health care" OR "Hospital" OR "connected medical device" OR "medical device" OR "medical IoT" OR "healthcare device" OR "IoHT" OR "IoMT" OR "MIoT" OR "networked medical devices" OR "medical cyber-physical system" OR "Health IoT" OR "Internet of Medical Things" OR "IoT healthcare" OR "medical device security") AND ("cybersecurity training " OR "cybersecurity awareness" OR "cybersecurity training delivery" OR "cybersecurity training design" OR "cybersecurity training evaluation" OR "cybersecurity training management" OR "cybersecurity awareness delivery" OR "cybersecurity awareness design" OR "cybersecurity awareness evaluation" OR "cybersecurity awareness management" or "cybersecurity") AND ("approaches" OR "frameworks" OR "models" OR "practices" OR "cyber practices" OR "best practices") AND ("threats" OR "incidents" OR "risks" OR "mitigation action" OR "safeguard" OR "risk reduction" OR "threat mitigation") AND ("psychology" OR "psychological aspect" OR "psychological behavior" OR "emotional psychology" OR "social psychology" OR "psychology of emotions" OR "emotional states" OR "emotional states of staff")) AND (LIMITTO (LANGUAGE, "English"))	7	1. Search Field: Article title, Abstract, Keywords; 2. Publications: All types; 3. Language: English; 4. Search date range: None.
ACM	[[All: "healthcare"] OR [All: "health care"] OR [All: "hospital"] OR [All: "connected medical device"] OR [All: "medical device"] OR [All: "medical iot"] OR [All: "healthcare device"] OR [All: "ioht"] OR [All: "iomt"] OR [All: "miot"] OR [All: "networked medical devices"] OR [All: "medical cyber-physical system"] OR [All: "health iot"] OR [All: "internet of medical things"] OR [All: "iot healthcare"] OR [All: "medical device security"]] AND [[All: "cybersecurity training "] OR [All: "cybersecurity awareness"] OR [All: "cybersecurity training delivery"] OR [All: "cybersecurity training design"] OR [All: "cybersecurity training evaluation"] OR [All: "cybersecurity training management"] OR [All: "cybersecurity awareness delivery"] OR [All: "cybersecurity awareness design"] OR [All: "cybersecurity awareness evaluation"] OR [[All: "cybersecurity awareness management"] AND [All: or "cybersecurity"]]] AND [[All: "approaches"] OR [All: "frameworks"] OR [All: "models"] OR [All: "practices"] OR [All: "cyber practices"] OR [All: "best practices"]] AND [[All: "threats"] OR [All: "incidents"] OR [All: "risks"] OR [All: "mitigation action"] OR [All: "safeguard"] OR [All: "risk reduction"] OR [All: "threat mitigation"]] AND [[All: "psychology"] OR [All: "psychological aspect"] OR [All: "psychological behavior"] OR [All: "emotional psychology"] OR [All: "social psychology"] OR [All: "psychology of emotions"] OR [All: "emotional states"] OR [All: "emotional states of staff"]] AND [E-Publication Date: (01/01/2015 TO 12/31/2025)] AND [Language: "English"]	151	1. Search Field: Searched The ACM Guide to Computing Literature; 2. Publications: All types; 3. Language: English; 4. Search date range: 2015–2025.
IEEE Xplore	("healthcare" OR "health care" OR "Hospital" OR "connected medical device" OR "medical device" OR "medical IoT" OR "healthcare device" OR "IoHT" OR "IoMT" OR "MIoT" OR "networked medical devices" OR "medical cyber-physical system" OR "Health IoT" OR "Internet of Medical Things" OR "IoT healthcare" OR "medical device security") AND ("cybersecurity training " OR "cybersecurity awareness" OR "cybersecurity training delivery" OR "cybersecurity training design" OR "cybersecurity training evaluation" OR "cybersecurity training management" OR "cybersecurity awareness delivery" OR "cybersecurity awareness design" OR "cybersecurity awareness evaluation" OR "cybersecurity awareness management" or "cybersecurity") AND ("approaches" OR "frameworks" OR "models" OR "practices" OR "cyber practices" OR "best practices")	18	1. Publications: journals, conferences; 2. Language: English; 3. Search date range: 2015–2025
Springer Link	("healthcare" OR "health care" OR "Hospital" OR "connected medical device" OR "medical device" OR "medical IoT" OR "healthcare device" OR "IoHT" OR "IoMT" OR "MIoT" OR "networked medical devices" OR "medical cyber-physical system" OR "Health IoT" OR "Internet of Medical Things" OR "IoT healthcare" OR "medical device security") AND ("cybersecurity training " OR "cybersecurity awareness" OR "cybersecurity training delivery" OR "cybersecurity training design" OR "cybersecurity training evaluation" OR "cybersecurity training management" OR "cybersecurity awareness delivery" OR "cybersecurity awareness design" OR "cybersecurity awareness evaluation" OR "cybersecurity awareness management" or "cybersecurity") AND ("approaches" OR "frameworks" OR "models" OR "practices" OR "cyber practices" OR "best practices") AND ("threats" OR "incidents" OR "risks" OR "mitigation action" OR "safeguard" OR "risk reduction" OR "threat mitigation") AND ("psychology" OR "psychological aspect" OR "psychological behavior" OR "emotional psychology" OR "social psychology" OR "psychology of emotions" OR "emotional states" OR "emotional states of staff")	6	1. Publications: journals, conferences; 2. Language: none; 3. Search date range: 2015–2025

Appendix C: Complete Search strategy

Source	Boolean Search	Search Result	Screening protocol
PubMed	("healthcare" OR "health care" OR "Hospital" OR "connected medical device" OR "medical device" OR "medical IoT" OR "healthcare device" OR "IoHT" OR "IoMT" OR "MIoT" OR "networked medical devices" OR "medical cyber-physical system" OR "Health IoT" OR "Internet of Medical Things" OR "IoT healthcare" OR "medical device security") AND ("cybersecurity training " OR "cybersecurity awareness" OR "cybersecurity training delivery" OR "cybersecurity training design" OR "cybersecurity training evaluation" OR "cybersecurity training management" OR "cybersecurity awareness delivery" OR "cybersecurity awareness design" OR "cybersecurity awareness evaluation" OR "cybersecurity awareness management" or "cybersecurity") AND ("approaches" OR "frameworks" OR "models" OR "practices" OR "cyber practices" OR "best practices") AND ("threats" OR "incidents" OR "risks" OR "mitigation action" OR "safeguard" OR "risk reduction" OR "threat mitigation") AND ("psychology" OR "psychological aspect" OR "psychological behavior" OR "emotional psychology" OR "social psychology" OR "psychology of emotions" OR "emotional states" OR "emotional states of staff")	0	No settings
Google Scholar	"medical device" "healthcare " "cybersecurity training " "cybersecurity awareness" "approaches" "practices" "frameworks" "models" "psychology	41	1. Publications: All types; 2. Search date range: 2015 – 2025; 3. Configuration: Where my words occur anywhere in the article.

b) Second Method

Source	Boolean Search	Search Result	Screening protocol
Scopus	(TITLE-ABS-KEY("Cybersecurity" OR "information security" OR "cyber hygiene" OR "Information system security" OR "Organizational cybersecurity" OR "computer security" OR "cyber security") AND TITLE-ABS-KEY("Healthcare" OR "Healthcare information technology" OR "health care" OR "health care professionals" OR "healthcare information system" OR "delivery of health care" OR "healthcare information security") AND TITLE-ABS-KEY("Cognitive dissonance" OR "Psychological incentive" OR "Affect" OR "Stressors" OR "Coping responses" OR "Risk Perception" OR "Risk Understanding" OR "Emotion" OR "affect" OR "psychological" OR "emotion" OR "Psychological capital" OR "Information security fatigue" OR "Information security–related stress" OR "emotions" OR "psychological capital" OR "Emotion-focused coping" OR "personality traits" OR "dark traits" OR "psychology" OR "positive emotions" OR "emotional intelligence" OR "cognitive bias" OR "negative emotions" OR "Mindfulness" OR "Security-Related Stress" OR "Technostress" OR "stress") AND TITLE-ABS-KEY("awareness" OR "training" OR "cybercriminal activities" OR "information security awareness" OR "Cybersecurity training" OR "Employee awareness" OR "Cyber resilience" OR "awareness training")) AND PUBYEAR > 2014 AND PUBYEAR < 2026 AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE,"English")) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE,"ar") OR LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE,"cp") OR LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE,"ch") OR LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE,"bk") OR LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE,"re"))	117	1. Search Field: Article title, Abstract, Keywords; 2. Publications: Article, Conference paper, Review, Book chapter, Book; 3. Language: English; 4. Search date range: 2015-2025.

Appendix C: Complete Search strategy

Source	Boolean Search	Search Result	Screening protocol
ACM	[[All: "cybersecurity"] OR [All: "information security"] OR [All: "cyber hygiene"] OR [All: "information system security"] OR [All: "organizational cybersecurity"] OR [All: "computer security"] OR [All: "cyber security"]] AND [[All: "healthcare"] OR [All: "healthcare information technology"] OR [All: "health care"] OR [All: "health care professionals"] OR [All: "healthcare information system"] OR [All: "delivery of health care"] OR [All: "healthcare information security"]] AND [[All: "cognitive dissonance"] OR [All: "psychological incentive"] OR [All: "affect"] OR [All: "stressors"] OR [All: "coping responses"] OR [All: "risk perception"] OR [All: "risk understanding"] OR [All: "emotion"] OR [All: "affect"] OR [All: "psychological"] OR [All: "emotion"] OR [All: "psychological capital"] OR [All: "information security fatigue"] OR [All: "information security-related stress"] OR [All: "emotions"] OR [All: "psychological capital"] OR [All: "emotion-focused coping"] OR [All: "personality traits"] OR [All: "dark traits"] OR [All: "psychology"] OR [All: "positive emotions"] OR [All: "emotional intelligence"] OR [All: "cognitive bias"] OR [All: "negative emotions"] OR [All: "mindfulness"] OR [All: "security-related stress"] OR [All: "technostress"] OR [All: "stress"]] AND [[All: "awareness"] OR [All: "training"] OR [All: "cybercriminal activities"] OR [All: "information security awareness"] OR [All: "cybersecurity training"] OR [All: "employee awareness"] OR [All: "cyber resilience"] OR [All: "awareness training"]] AND [[All: "behaviour change"] OR [All: "protection-motivated behaviours"] OR [All: "behavioral change"] OR [All: "information security behavior"] OR [All: "motivated behavior"] OR [All: "behavioral information security"] OR [All: "motivation"] OR [All: "behavioral cybersecurity"]] AND [E-Publication Date: (01/01/2015 TO 12/31/2025)]	1232	1. Search Field: Searched The ACM Guide to Computing Literature; 2. Publications: All types; 3. Language: none; 4. Search date range: 2015–2025.
IEEE Xplore	("Cybersecurity" OR "information security" OR "cyber hygiene" OR "Information system security" OR "Organizational cybersecurity" OR "computer security" OR "cyber security") AND ("Healthcare" OR "Healthcare information technology" OR "health care" OR "health care professionals" OR "healthcare information system" OR "delivery of health care" OR "healthcare information security") AND ("Cognitive dissonance" OR "Psychological incentive" OR "Affect" OR "Stressors" OR "Coping responses" OR "Risk Perception" OR "Risk Understanding" OR "Emotion" OR "affect" OR "psychological" OR "emotion" OR "Psychological capital" OR "Information security fatigue" OR "Information security-related stress" OR "emotions" OR "psychological capital" OR "Emotion-focused coping" OR "personality traits" OR "dark traits" OR "psychology" OR "positive emotions" OR "emotional intelligence" OR "cognitive bias" OR "negative emotions" OR "Mindfulness" OR "Security-Related Stress" OR "Technostress" OR "stress") AND ("awareness" OR "training" OR "cybercriminal activities" OR "information security awareness" OR "Cybersecurity training" OR "Employee awareness" OR "Cyber resilience" OR "awareness training")	35	1. Publications: journals, conferences; 2. Language: English; 3. Search date range: 2015–2025
Springer Link	("Cybersecurity" OR "information security" OR "cyber hygiene" OR "Information system security" OR "Organizational cybersecurity" OR "computer security" OR "cyber security") AND ("Healthcare" OR "Healthcare information technology" OR "health care" OR "health care professionals" OR "healthcare information system" OR "delivery of health care" OR "healthcare information security") AND ("Cognitive dissonance" OR "Psychological incentive" OR "Affect" OR "Stressors" OR "Coping responses" OR "Risk Perception" OR "Risk Understanding" OR "Emotion" OR "affect" OR "psychological" OR "emotion" OR "Psychological capital" OR "Information security fatigue" OR "Information security-related stress" OR "emotions" OR "psychological capital" OR "Emotion-focused coping" OR "personality traits" OR "dark traits" OR "psychology" OR "positive emotions" OR "emotional intelligence" OR "cognitive bias" OR "negative emotions" OR "Mindfulness" OR "Security-Related Stress" OR "Technostress" OR "stress") AND ("awareness" OR "training" OR "cybercriminal activities" OR "information security awareness" OR "Cybersecurity training" OR "Employee awareness" OR "Cyber resilience" OR "awareness training") AND ("behaviour change" OR "protection-motivated behaviours" OR "Behavioral change" OR "information security behavior" OR "Motivated behavior" OR "Behavioral Information Security" OR "motivation" OR "behavioral cybersecurity")	333	1. Publications: journals, conferences; 2. Language: none; 3. Search date range: 2015–2025

Appendix C: Complete Search strategy

Source	Boolean Search	Search Result	Screening protocol
PubMed	("Cybersecurity" OR "information security" OR "cyber hygiene" OR "Information system security" OR "Organizational cybersecurity" OR "computer security" OR "cyber security") AND ("Healthcare" OR "Healthcare information technology" OR "health care" OR "health care professionals" OR "healthcare information system" OR "delivery of health care" OR "healthcare information security") AND ("Cognitive dissonance" OR "Psychological incentive" OR "Affect" OR "Stressors" OR "Coping responses" OR "Risk Perception" OR "Risk Understanding" OR "Emotion" OR "affect" OR "psychological" OR "emotion" OR "Psychological capital" OR "Information security fatigue" OR "Information security-related stress" OR "emotions" OR "psychological capital" OR "Emotion-focused coping" OR "personality traits" OR "dark traits" OR "psychology" OR "positive emotions" OR "emotional intelligence" OR "cognitive bias" OR "negative emotions" OR "Mindfulness" OR "Security-Related Stress" OR "Technostress" OR "stress") AND ("awareness" OR "training" OR "cybercriminal activities" OR "information security awareness" OR "Cybersecurity training" OR "Employee awareness" OR "Cyber resilience" OR "awareness training") AND ("behaviour change" OR "protection-motivated behaviours" OR "Behavioral change" OR "information security behavior" OR "Motivated behavior" OR "Behavioral Information Security" OR "motivation" OR "behavioral cybersecurity")	3	No settings